

A Study on the Construction of Experience Design in Creative Life Industry – Take Shin-gang Incense Artistic Culture Garden in Chia-yi County as an example

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Abstract

Starting in 2002, the development blueprint of the cultural creative industry has been proposed by the administrator in Taiwan, and which includes the creative life industry policy of transforming the traditional industry. Generally speaking, the creative life industry focuses on the inborn features such as the culture, the technology and the knowledge of traditional industries. When these features are used to combine with the contemporary living style and culture, they provide the learning and experience of the ordinary customers through the process of the cultural industrialization. Eventually, it corresponds to the development tendency of the experiential experience. In this study, Incense Artistic Culture Garden locates Shin-gang town, Chia-yi County, Taiwan, is exemplified. This study conducts literature review, environmental behavior observation and interview in order to figure out what are the fundamental elements of the experience design in the garden and the strategy of creating the experience of the visitors. The main conclusions are as follows:

1. The group of the experience design elements depends on the blueprint of the experiential theme of the business.
2. The use of the experience design elements governs or is governed by the other and they depend on each other.
3. The life experiences composed of the experience design elements can further the formation of the style society.

Conference theme: experience modeling

Keywords: Creative life industry, Experience design, Shin-gang Incense Artistic Culture Garden, Six senses

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

As pointed out by Li (2006), ‘the development of the cultural creativity business provides the abundant living experience atmosphere; it does not only aggrandize the happiness of the people but also an invisible resource of the business competitiveness of the country.’¹ Starting in 2002, the development blueprint of the cultural creativity has been proposed by the administrator in Taiwan, and the blueprint includes the creativity life business policy of transforming the traditional business. General speaking, the creative life business emphasizes the inborn features such as the culture, the technology and the knowledge of the traditional business. When these features are used to combine with the contemporary living style and culture, they provide the learning and the experience of being involved to the ordinary customers through the process of the cultural industrialization. Eventually, it corresponds to the contemporary developmental tendency of the experiential experience.

1.2 Goal

The molding of the experiential experience is a process of stimulating the intrinsic feeling by the extrinsic stimuli. The quality of the experience design has a decisive effect to the molding of the experience; the performance of experience design comes from the mutual use of many different elements. But, to determine which elements is usable and how they form the experience design and create experiential experience for tourists are the focus of this study. Hence, the two goals of the study in this paper follow the core conception to be as follows:

1. To understand the fundamental elements of the experience design in the garden and their effects.
2. To discuss effective strategies of forming the experience of the attendants.

1.3 Designation of the study

This study takes Shin-gang Incense Artistic Cultural Garden as an example, which locates Shin-gang town, Chia-yi County, Taiwan. The main research methods include literature review, environmental behavior observation², and profound interview to understand the construction of the experience design elements. The study involves totally 10 subjects, who are numbered in the

¹ Retrieved from: http://www.youthhub.tw//exchange/pool/quarterly_q4/down01_1.pdf, Jun 5th, 2008.

² The garden includes two main parts and therefore the practice of the observation is divided into the outdoor area and the experience course in cultural house. During the research, the researchers conduct 1) fixed location · 2) complete participant, and interview the observational targets after the observation. The focus of the interview is how the subjects feel about the different kinds of the experiential activities in the garden.

order of A01, A02 and so on. The subject number is followed by ‘-N’ to mark the number of the interview (e.g. A01-1).

1.4 Research Process

Figure 1. The flow chart of this research

2. Literature review

2.1 Creative life industry

Based on 《2004 Taiwan Annual Report on Cultural and Creative Industry》, creative life industry stands for that ‘through the integration of the core conceptions of the life industry with the creativity, a business with the profound experience and high-quality beauty can be provided.’ Creative life industry emerges from the change of the economical environment changes. Since 2002, “Challenge 2008: National Development Plan” and “Cultural and Creative Industry Development Plan” are positively promoted in Taiwan to develop creative life industry. The main purpose is to help the business to establish its own cultural value based on its knowledge resources such as history, technology of producing, culture. It also aims to integrate the resources and to promote the complex management and increase the supplementary value of the business, which helps the continuous development of the business.

The three intrinsic features of creative life industry are ‘core knowledge’, ‘profound experience’ and ‘high-quality beauty’. However, if there is no any creative and culturally profound design strategy in ‘profound experience’, the attendants might be depressed with their desire of learning ‘core knowledge’ and pursuance of ‘high-quality beauty’.

2.2 Experience

2.2.1 The definition

The general definition of experience is an observation and a description of the rule change in the whole third wave of economic reform that ‘in terms of the uniqueness, experience is a conclusion of the problem observation from the perspective of the market demands (i.e. what do

customers acquire from the revolution?) rather than the enterprise supplies (i.e. what do enterprises provide in the revolution?).’ (Jiang 2002)

Experience concerns with the psychological sensibility of human beings. All the people, events and objects, which provoke inner emotion, are parts of experience, either good ones or bad ones. In *The New Shorter Oxford English Oxford English Dictionary*, experience is defined as the acquisition of knowledge and skills by doing, seeing and feeling any events. Moreover, experience is distinctive in different level of sensibility of an individual. Pine II and Gilmore (1999) define experience as “an economical product originated from service, which is initiated from the customer’s consumption. The consumers are involved through the demonstration of experience to form a unique feeling and unforgettable values.”

2.2.2 Strategic Experiential Modules (SEMs)

Schmitt (1999) is inspired by the interaction among sense contact 、 touch contact 、 cognition system in mind modules and import the correlation between the action and its meaning, which psychologists and sociologists highly emphasize. He divides experience into five categories and builds up a psychological experience model of the consumers, which are so-called Strategic Experiential Modules (SEMs). The composition of the module includes sense, feel, think, act and relate.

Aspect	Contents
Sense	‘Sense’ means the perceptual stimuli, which attracts consumers through the sensation of their eyes, ears, mouth, nose and hands.
Feel	‘Feel’ means to provoke the inner emotion of consumers.
Think	‘Think’ focuses on the meditation of the knowledge learning and tries to evoke the brainstorm, involvement and leads to paradigm shift.
Act	‘Act’ emphasizes the correlation between the action experience and the life style.
Relate	‘Relate’ encapsulates all the four levels above and affects potential group members through the group perspective.

Table 1. Aspects of Experiential Marketing strategies

3. A case study

3.1 Shin-gang Incense Artistic Culture Garden

Shin-gang Incense Artistic Culture Garden mainly features the culture preservation, the technology of incense production and the relationship between the incense and life. The garden so far can be separate as 「Herbs & Spice Area」 and 「Incense Artistic Museum」 and the arrangement of the two main areas is as in Table 2:

Field Plan of Herbs and Spice Area	Floor Plan of Incense Artistic Museum
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Incense of hand make 3. Incense-making performance 4. Fish pool 5. Incense-drying field 6. Park 7. Restaurant 8. Bed and Breakfast 9. Ba-gua planting 10. Camphor area 11. Maple area 12. Algom area 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lobby 2. Cultural incense 3. Incense of daily life 4. Artistic incense 5. Natural incense 6. The steps of incense production 7. Perfume & style 8. Cinestrip Incense 9. DIY classroom 10. Incense of Shin-gang 11. Temporary exhibition area

Table 2. The planar plans of Herbs & Spice Area & Incense Artistic Museum

3.2 The experience design of the garden

As shown in Table 3, the garden has two main topics with various sub-areas. The core conceptions of the design of the two main thematic areas are particularized as follows after the interview with the operator and the designer:

1. Herbs & Spice area: Chen³ (2008) claims that “in order to express the professionalism of the incense production business and the variety of the incense, the design of the garden aims at a multi-functional life experience place, which covers the performance, gardening, food, demonstration and accommodation.” The integration among ‘visage’, ‘object’, ‘people’ and ‘elaboration’ can smooth the process of knowledge learning and understanding of the customers.
2. Incense Artistic Museum: This is a local cultural museum that combines knowledge learning, cultural inheritance and aromatic experience together. Through the demonstration designing, space arrangement and life experience, it can raise the possibility of the daily practice of the customers. Li (2007), who is the designer of the garden, claims that “for the representation

³ The operator of the garden.

of the developmental origin of the religion and the incense business, the cultural conceptions of incense such as the art of incense, the material of incense, the production of incense and the worship with incense are integrated. Combined with the sensational and the rational demonstration to represent the practice of the incense art in our daily life, these conceptions implant the understanding of the incense art in the visitor's mind.”

Based on the above descriptions, the study categorizes the experience design and representation of the two topic areas according to the technique and the object in different demonstration zones as in Table 3:

Thematic Area	Exhibit Area	Exhibit Planning	Experience Object
Herbs and Spice Area	Ba-gua flower bed	To plant general herbs in the garden next to the Eight Trigrams pavilion and put an illustration board nearby the garden.	Herbs
	Incense of hand make	To demonstrate the traditional process of the incense production directly and the visitors can have a concrete understanding with it.	Incense production tools, sun-drying frame
	Restaurant	To cook with the natural herb spices to express the conception of the healthy and delicious diet.	Various dishes
	Bed and Breakfast	Rooms are decorated with various styles and each particular incense-cone is provided to the customers according to each decoration style.	Stylish room decoration
Incense Artistic Museum	Lobby	1. To design lamps with the incense art to represent the creative application of the incense. 2. To magnify the size of "Along the River During the Qingming Festival" in the incense store to emphasize the history of the incense industry.	Lamps of incense, Along the River During the Qingming Festival, logo
	Cultural Incense	To introduce the origin and the history of incense with geography, religion and old Chinese myths. The room is also arranged according to the old-age decoration in a study to demonstrate the situation of the use of incense.	Demonstration board, old-age decoration, incense burner
	Incense in daily life	To introduce the relationship between the daily life and the use of incense.	Demonstration board
	Artistic Incense	To introduce natural camphor wood and Chinese cypress, which are used to be engraved as God statues, and to feel the odor of woods	God statue, natural timber
	Natural Incense	To put natural spices in different glass bottles with a illustration card to explain the name and the usage.	Dried herb materials
	Perfume & style	Potteries with different essence smells are exhibited, the attendants can purchase if they are interested in it.	Smell the potteries with incense
	The steps of incense production	To draw a comic style process of the incense production on aboard and recently it is represented tridimensionally with dolls made by the soil.	Soil dolls, illustration board on the wall
	Cinstrip Incense	The arrangement of the room focuses on the old-age high-class living style with the wallpaper,	Wallpaper, antique

		peony and the traditional Min-Dynasty furniture to create the situation of the use of incense in the old times.	furniture, peony
	DIY classroom	1. To use the powder with incense and water to mold the plant and human-like statues. 2. To put the incense powder with different smells in the traditional medicine cabinet. Visitors can pretend to be the boss of a Chinese drug store and make their own favorite sachet..	Medicine cabinet, prototypical powder statues
	others	The natural fragrance of a perforated sandal wood in the glass cabinet pervades in the cabinet and provides the visitors a direct experience.	A hundred-year sandalwood

Table 3. The Experience Design and manipulation of the thematic areas in Shin-gang Incense Artistic Cultural Garden

4. Analysis of the structure of the experience design

4.1 Thematic categories of experience in the garden

This study summarizes the description of experience of the 10 subjects and categorizes the similar experience into the same group, as shown in Table 4:

Experience Interview	Experience Concept	Senses	Design Performance
Seeing the incense factory.(A01-1)	Production and sale location	Eyes	Space demonstration
You know that they sale the incense right away after you saw the sun-drying incense. (A03-1)			
It is elegant to use the wallpaper, antique furniture and peony to represent the old-age in cinestrip incense. (A02-5)	Old-age situation of using incense.	Ears, eyes	
I think that it is pretty traditional when I see the indoor arrangement of the old-age bookman's desktop tools, who uses the incense a lot. (A05-6)			
You say incense artistry, but how can we call it without any fragrance inside? (A03-4)	There should be some fragrant in the hall.	Nose, eyes	Creation of atmosphere
The manager burns the sandalwood powder when we were visiting and different odors pervaded in the hall. (A07-3)			
Opening the bottle and smelling the natural fragrance of woods in a short distance can impress us a lot.(A01-4)	Smelling herb materials and woods are available	Nose	
I feel pretty good because we can directly smell and feel some exhibits. (A02-3)			
It is very comfortable for me to smell the most natural odors here. (A05-4)			
The pendant lamp in the hall is made with the stick of incense, which is pretty much of their feature of the incense production. (A04-2)	To use the lamp designed by yourself.	Eyes	Experience products
The lamps decorated along the corridor outside the rooms of B&B are very special. (A05-8)			
Many demonstrative potteries have different	Products as	Nose	

essences inside and we can purchase as we want with the instruction. (A09-8)	exhibits		
The ring incense burns in the exhibition is there own product. (A03-5)			
It is better have a contemporary arrangement and they should teach us how to use the incense according to different features of each room. (A02-5)	Experience the creation of a fragrant life	Eyes	Life experience design
The room we lived in has a special name, and they provided 'ocean flavor' incense for us. (A05-6)			
Illustrators elaborate on a few common herbal spices. If we drink the flower tea or the healthy tea someday, we should know what the benefits of their materials are. (A05-5)	Incense as food condiments	Ears, eyes	
A housewife like me is interested in which spice is suitable to flavor. In the place where I can smell the spices, I asked the illustrator how to use them and where to buy them. (A04-3)			
The experience of sachet DIY is similar to that in Lavender Forest; you can choose your own favorite flavors and put them into a small bag. If you put it in the closet or toilet, it can eliminate the stink and make the place fragrant. (A08-7)	To join DIY events	Hands	Participatory experience
Children can have the experience for fun and memorial. When they were playing, they said that their hands smell good. (A09-11)			
I have bought the violet essence and I want to put it in my office. It has the effect of stabilizing my psychological condition. (A9-10)	Purchasing products in the garden	N/A	
I occasionally burn sandalwood incense at home. I bought their products for personal use, but also for the comparison. (A03-7)			
Only after I came here, I know an old story that there is a relationship between Nu Wa and incense from the illustrator. (A01-3)	To lead customer's intellective learning	Ears, eyes	Commentation
The illustrator had told us how to distinguish the quality of the incense with your nose. (A04-8)			
There is no procedure of the incense production so we didn't understand how incense is made. But after we went into the hall, we know the procedure with the illustration on the board. (A02-2)	Supplementary learning on the demonstration board.	Eyes, ears	
Incense industry had already existed in Qing Dynasty, and I think this is why they magnify a part of "Along the River During the Qingming Festival". (A03-1)			
They asked customers to provide their personal information to send the latest news or new year cards. I think that they did a good job. (A10-9)	Establish a good impression to the customers	Eyes, ears, mind	Friendly service
We went the tour by ourselves, but the managers still actively told us that we can open the potteries and smell the essence. So we felt that we're totally free and we worried nothing when			

opening the potteries and smelling. (A10-6)			
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Table 4. Analysis of Experience Design in the Garden by customers

In the result, the experiential design in the garden can be separated as seven categories: 1) The demonstration of the history and modern times connection in a space 2) Creation of the fragrant atmosphere 3) Products in the garden can be directly experienced 4) Life experience design correlated with the daily life 5) The practice of the experiential activity 6) Knowledge learning furthered by the illustration service 7) Positive service attitude. From the above categories, this study not only analyzes the sensation effect of the design but also the manipulation of ‘mind’ with the ‘positive service attitude’.

Schmitt (1999) points out that the more the involved sensations are, the more successful the experience is. Beyond the general sensation of eyes, ears, mouth, nose and hands, the feeling in the mind becomes the ‘sixth senses’. It is directly relevant between the service attitude of ‘customer first’ and the success of the experience creation to a high degree. However, this study argues that in the process of experience, the ‘sixth sense’ should be treated as a ‘bridge’ to lead customers to experience the themes in the garden. Therefore, we do not include the ‘sixth sense’ as one of the experiential forms.

4.2 The composition of Experience Design Elements (PAS)²

If we would like to further categorize the form of the experience in the garden, we can start it with the experience concept, the experience form and the extracted composition of PAS. It includes six main elements: 1) space 2) atmosphere 3) products 4) life style 5) act 6) service⁴.

The relevant analysis is summarized as in Table 5:

Experience Concept	Experience Term	Experience Performance	Experience Mode	Experience Element
The place of the incense production and sales.	Traditional, productive	Exhibition of history in a space	Watch	Place
Old-age situation of the use of incense				
Fragrance should be full of the exhibition hall.	Aromatic, elegant, natural	Creation of the aromatic atmosphere	Smell	Atmosphere
Herbal materials and woods should be available for sampling				
Experience the creation of the fragrant life	Common, practical	General living style design of the contents	Watch	Style
The use in the				

⁴ The illustration service and the service attitude are subcategories of the ‘general service’ and therefore this study treats both in the same category as the factors of the ‘general service’.

cooking				
Using the lamp with your own design	Creative, living	Experience the products in the garden by yourself	Use	Product
Products of the garden as exhibits.				
Participate DIY experience activities	Idealistic, participatory	The practice of the experience activities	Manipulate	Activity
Purchase the products in the garden				
To induct the customer to learn intellectually	Active, friendly	Illustration service helps knowledge learning	Listen	Service
Supplementary learning from the demonstrative board and the exhibits				
To establish the positive impression in customers' mind.		Positive and active service attitude	Feel	

Table 5. Analysis of Experience Design Elements

4.3 The process of Experience Design strategies of the garden

From above analysis, the Incense Artistic Culture Garden displayed the following six ways to attract tourists with profound experiential image by performing the six elements (see Figure 5):

- (1) Space and exhibition,
- (2) Guide and interpretation,
- (3) Creation of aromatic atmosphere,
- (4) Experience and try the products,
- (5) Participate DIY experience activities,
- (6) Positive service.

This study discovered that the experiential design of the Garden is diverse, assisted with “senses” as the “media⁵” to create stimulation experience. Through this way, the experience designers expect tourists to like the experience design and friendly service from the bottom of their hearts; or, through rational thinking, they may have deep cognition on the culture heritage and artistry preservation. The above two ways both lead them willingly to make chances and perform those experiences in their life, and become a life style group which “is fond of using incense in daily life.” Therefore, this study believes that the Strategic Experiential Modules from Schmitt (1999) not only can be used as experience marketing strategies, but also the methods and processes in exploring how the experiential experience formed for the tourists of Incense Artistic Culture Garden.

⁵ During the process of experience, the mentioned senses: eyes, ears, mouth, nose, hands, and mind are considered as the media for the tourists to obtain experiential experience, which are only used to stimulate the formation of experience. Therefore, the senses are not included as one of the experience design elements.

However, this research also pointed out that, the use of experience design elements were depended on the setting of “the experiential theme.” That is to say, the experience design may become more complicated and lead tourists to confusion if the experiential theme is not confined to 1) incense and life, 2) the culture and history of incense. Combining all the above statements and taking the Incense Artistic Culture Garden as an example, the structure of performing experience elements and forming experiential experience is shown in the Figure 2:

Figure 2. The steps of forming the Experiential Experience strategies in Shin-gang Incense Artistic Cultural Garden

5. Conclusion

The experience design of the Incense Artistic Culture Garden came from the performance of the following elements: space, atmosphere, product, style, motion, and service. Whether the experience design is good or bad will directly affect the formation of customers' experiential experiences. A good experience attracts people to participate by disseminating the experience from one to another. By contrast, a terrible experience causes the loss of customers. Therefore, the using of design elements becomes very important. This study concludes as follows:

1. The group of the experience design elements depends on the blueprint of the experiential theme of the business:

The theme must be set up with the experience. What we can discover from the design of the garden is that the settlement of the theme is influenced by the living and cultural development of the business. Moreover, how the administrator understands and plans for the theme affects the overall development of the experimental contents and the use of the design elements.

2. The use of the experience design elements governs or is governed by the other and they depend on each other:

The experience design elements include space, atmosphere, product, living style, activity and service. They are in a relationship of parents and children and they are interdependent among themselves. For example, the garden must design for the space, the products and the service to provide the resource of the sensational stimulation. On the other hand, if the supplementary learning such as the illustration service is not available, despite of the experience design of the space and the products, the customers may still not understand the design. Therefore, the use and the manipulation of the experience elements have their integrity.

3. The life experiences composed of the experience design elements can further the formation of the style society:

The three intrinsic features of creative life industry are 'core knowledge', 'profound experience' and 'high-quality beauty'. Among these features, 'profound experience' comes from the use and the representation of the experience elements; the experience affects the knowledge learning and the sensibility of beauty. The garden provides the happiness feeling brought by the incense in different parts of the daily life to the customers and leads them to meditate at the same time with the space, the products and the service. Furthermore, the customers are encouraged to seek the application of their behaviors in the daily life to form a particular style society.

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